

A STUDY OF THE HYDRATED COPPER SALTS OF BF_3O^{2-} , BeF_4^{2-} AND SO_4^{2-} IONS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

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The powder photography of $\text{CuBF}_3\text{O}\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ has shown that it is not isomorphous with $\text{CuSO}_4\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, while $\text{CuBeF}_4\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is isomorphous with $\text{CuSO}_4\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$. All these three compounds, however, form mixed crystals. These three compounds were heated to 250° . The loss in weight of $\text{CuBF}_3\text{O}\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ suggests the formation of CuO . This has been verified by X-ray as well as by chemical analysis. $\text{CuBeF}_4\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ at 250° affords a mixture of CuF_2 , BeF_2 and traces of BeO . No anhydrous compound, such as CuBF_3O or CuBeF_4 has been obtained.

The three anions, BeF_4^{2-} , BF_3O^{2-} and SO_4^{2-} are isosteric and isoelectronic. The chemical analogy between BeF_4^{2-} and SO_4^{2-} ions has been established (Ray, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1931, 201, 289; 1932, 205, 257). The X-ray diffraction study on some of these fluoroberyllates has also been carried out (Mukherjee, *Curr. Sci.*, 1934, 3, 66). The chemistry of oxyfluoroborate ion has been studied recently by Mitra (*Science & Culture*, 1953, 19, 106) and Ray and Mitra (unpublished). The similarity in chemical properties between the salts of SO_4^{2-} and BF_3O^{2-} ions has been proved in general, and barium or lead sulphates have been shown to be isomorphous with the corresponding oxyfluoroborates.

BF_3O^{2-} ion, however, is not as stable as SO_4^{2-} ion. At higher temperatures BF_3O^{2-} ion breaks down and BF_3 (gas) is evolved. The SO_4^{2-} ion, on the other hand, is very stable and SO_3 leaves the molecule only at a very high temperature. The central element being metallic in character, no such phenomenon is seen with the BeF_4^{2-} ion.

The effect of heating the pentahydrated copper salts of BF_3O^{2-} , BeF_4^{2-} and SO_4^{2-} ions at different temperatures was studied by the chemical analysis of the compounds obtained at different temperatures, and also by X-ray diffraction spectra. The present paper describes the results.

EXPERIMENTAL

A. R. quality pentahydrated copper sulphate was used. Copper fluoroberyllate pentahydrate and copper oxyfluoroborate pentahydrate were prepared by the methods described before. All the compounds were recrystallised.

The results of analysis of $\text{CuBeF}_4\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{CuBF}_3\text{O}\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ are : (Found : Cu, 26.52 ; Be, 3.62 ; F, 31.73. Calc. for $\text{CuBeF}_4\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Cu, 26.63 ; Be, 3.78 ; F, 31.84%) and (Found : Cu, 26.84 ; B, 4.50 ; F, 23.90. Calc. for $\text{CuBF}_3\text{O}\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Cu, 26.83 ; B, 4.56 ; F, 24.05%).

The powder photography of these three compounds was taken at about 30° . Tables I and II record the results.

TABLE I
CuBF₃O₅H₂O.

d.	Intensity.	d.	Intensity.
4.75	v s	1.71	m
4.36	v s	1.57	m
3.48	v s	1.42	w
2.69	m	1.38	w
2.38	m	1.34	w
2.16	s	1.29	w
1.91	v s	1.27	w

TABLE II
CuBeF₄.5H₂O.

d.	Intensity.	d.	Intensity.
5.45	v s	2.42	m
4.67	s	2.33	w
4.02	s	2.14	w
3.73	s	2.05	m
3.44	w	1.91	w
3.27	m	1.83	w
3.04	w	1.77	w
2.75	w	1.38	w

N.B. v s = very strong, s = strong, m = medium, w = weak.

The powder picture of CuSO₄.5H₂O has been reported before. The picture which was taken during the present investigation agreed with the one reported earlier. Hence, results are not given here.

The powder pattern clearly reveals that CuSO₄.5H₂O is isomorphous with CuBeF₄.5H₂O, while the structure of CuBF₃O₅H₂O is different. It might be mentioned in this connection that in spite of this difference CuSO₄.5H₂O formed mixed crystals with CuBF₃O₅H₂O.

Copper in CuSO₄.5H₂O is at the centre of an irregular octahedron, the two distorted poles of which are occupied by oxygen atoms belonging to SO₄²⁻ groups (Beevens and Lipson, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1934, **A146**, 570; Krishnan and Mukherjee, *Phys. Rev.*, 1938, **54**, 533). In CuBeF₄.5H₂O, fluorine atoms are obviously situated at the two poles. It may be suggested that in BF₃O²⁻ ion all the four atoms situated at the four corners of the tetrahedron are not the same, and hence, distortions caused by them are not uniform. The exact reason for this anomalous behaviour, however, demands further study.

The compounds were heated to 250° and the losses in % weight of the compounds at different temperatures were recorded (Table III).

TABLE III

Temp.	CuBF ₃ O ₅ H ₂ O.	CuBeF ₄ .5H ₂ O.	CuSO ₄ .5H ₂ O.
50°	3.61%	11.85%	20.32%
60°	4.03	18.50	23.03
80°	9.68	28.50	28.66
90°	60.24	32.95	28.85
100°	60.80	33.90	29.09
120°	62.00	34.93	29.20
130°	62.70	35.43	29.25
150°	63.80	35.85	29.27
160°	64.34	36.19	30.80
180°	65.39	37.58	33.55
190°	66.27	37.92	34.33
200°	66.27	38.11	35.18
220°	66.51	38.28	35.26
240°	66.51	38.36	35.39
250°	66.51	38.36	35.48

It was observed that from 80°-90° there was a sharp change in $\text{CuBF}_3\text{O}_4\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$. In the vicinity of 80°, this compound lost only one molecule of water. Loss in wt. at 80° = 9.68% (calc. for $\text{CuBF}_3\text{O}_4\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, loss = 7.15%).

When the remaining four molecules of water left the compound, the crystal structure was broken and BF_3 was simultaneously evolved. It is interesting to note in this connection that four out of five molecules of water in $\text{CuSO}_4\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ are in the same plane with the copper atom and these only take part in the formation of octahedron, mentioned above.

At 250°, 66.51% of the compound was lost. Theoretically therefore, this compound should be CuO . (Loss calculated for CuO from $\text{CuBF}_3\text{O}_4\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ = 66.32). Chemical analysis of the compound is (Found : Cu, 79.72%. Calc. for CuO : Cu, 79.89%).

The spacings, calculated from the powder picture of the compound, are shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV

$\text{CuBF}_3\text{O}_4\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (after being heated to 250°).

<i>d</i>	...	2.50	2.31	1.84	1.71	1.57	1.50	1.41	1.37	1.30	1.16	1.09	1.01
Intensity	...	v s	v s	w	w	w	m	m	w	w	w	w	w

This picture was compared with the standard spacings given for CuO , and proved to be identical.

In the case of copper fluoroberyllate, water molecules started to escape rapidly before 80°. The crystal structure was also automatically broken at this temperature. The present investigation could not identify any anhydrous compound such as CuBeF_4 .

As the fluoride of beryllium is not volatile, a mixture of BeO , BeF_2 and CuF_2 has been found to be formed at 250°. It has been shown before that chemically pure BeF_2 is obtained only when fluoroberyllate is heated in an inert atmosphere. Under ordinary conditions a mixture of BeO and BeF_2 always results. (Loss in wt. observed at 250° = 38.36%. Calc. for the conversion of $\text{CuBeF}_4\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ to $\text{CuF}_2\cdot \text{BeO}$ = 47.07%. Calc. for the conversion of $\text{CuBeF}_4\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ to $\text{CuF}_2\cdot \text{BeF}_2$ = 37.8%).

The presence of CuF_2 was verified by X-ray as well as chemical analysis. The powder picture revealed only the presence of CuF_2 . Beryllium was, however, found by chemical analysis. Due to the deliquescent nature of BeF_2 , the X-ray picture revealed the presence of $\text{CuF}_2\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ rather than anhydrous CuF_2 .

TABLE V

$\text{CuBeF}_4\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (heated to 250°).

<i>d</i>	...	4.73	3.52	2.56	2.44	2.14	1.96	1.61	1.50	1.33	1.22
Intensity	...	v s	w	s	w	w	m	w	w	w	w

This picture was compared with the standard spacings given for $\text{CuF}_2\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and proved to be identical.

The results of analysis of this compound are also given below.

TABLE VI

	% Cu.	% F.	% Be.
Found :	45.88	46.31	6.22
CuF ₂ .BeF ₃ requires :	42.79	51.14	6.07
CuF ₂ .BeO requires :	50.21	30.00	7.12

In the case of CuSO₄.5H₂O, anhydrous CuSO₄ is formed, but this work has been reported previously so that detailed descriptions are not given here.

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